

SPATIAL EFFICIENCY OF ROMANIA'S DEVELOPMENT REGIONS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT: The study assesses the spatial efficiency of Romania's counties and development regions from the perspective of sustainable development. Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) was used to calculate spatial efficiency, and A-P model (Andersen and Petersen) was used to rank efficient units (those with a score of 1.000) to assess superefficiency. The results of the study are graphically translated into four maps. The average efficiency of Romania's counties is 0.945 and the average efficiency of development regions is 0.986. Almost all development regions are efficient, with the only inefficient region being the Sud-Est region (0.887). The development regions with the highest superefficiency scores are located in the western part of Romania. The highest score of superefficiency is registered by the București-Ilfov region (30.997), the capital of the country and its surroundings, the economic engine of Romania.

KEY WORDS: Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), development regions, spatial efficiency, superefficiency, sustainable development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Earth's population exceeded 8 billion at the end of 2022 (UN, 2022). The urban population, in the same year, was 57% (The World Bank, 2022). This percentage is constantly and rapidly growing worldwide, with more and more people preferring to live in urban areas every year. Every week, 1.25 billion inhabitants of the planet are included in the global urban population (Worldometer, 2023). It is estimated that 68% of the world's population will live in urban areas by 2050 (UN-DESA, 2018).

Romania's urban population (population living in municipalities and cities) has almost the same value as that recorded worldwide, 56.1% on January 1, 2023 (INS, 2023), one of the lowest shares at European level. However, this indicator has a higher value when other methodologies are used to calculate it. The World Bank (Heroiu et al., 2013, p. 21 and p. 26) calculated Romania's agglomeration index using its own methodology, called GDR 2009 (Global Development Report 2009: Reshaping Economic Geography). This index is equivalent to the urban population defined above. In 2000, the value of the agglomeration index was 65.2%. For an area to be considered urban (functional urban area), it must comply with two conditions: (1) the population density in that area must be at least 150 inhabitants/km² and (2) there must be a locality with at least 50,000 inhabitants in that area, including the areas surrounding it within a radius of 60 minutes (suburban and peri-urban settlements). Additionally, the World Bank (Dinamica..., 2020, p. 13) used the EC-OECD methodology to identify functional urban areas for each municipality and city in Romania. Thus, all localities where at least 15% of the workforce commutes to the urban core were identified. Following the application of this methodology, it turned out that 76% of Romania's population lives in the city or in a functional urban area.

Urbanization is therefore a process that is inevitably increasing in all countries of the world. This process contributes to economic growth, creates new jobs, develops infrastructure and improves the standard of living of residents situated in urban areas. However, in addition to the undeniable positive aspects,

urbanization also leads to the emergence of negative aspects in the development of cities, such as: uneven population density, traffic congestion, changing the structure of urban land usage and pollution of the natural environment.

On the other hand, for many cities, changing the structure of land usage is necessary to meet the daily needs of residents and the demands of economic development. The natural environment can suffer the most serious consequences of urbanisation due to various interacting factors (economy, society and culture), such as: reduced diversity of habitats and their quality, depletion of water resources, increased surface run-off, earth surface temperature and carbon dioxide emissions. Although the change in land usage will affect the environment, it will still provide many benefits to cities and their inhabitants (Tsou and Kuo, 2012).

Therefore, economic development leads to important changes in the environment. The concept of sustainable development was imposed worldwide by the Brundtland Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED), entitled "Our Common Future" in 1987. Together with other 192 countries of the world, Romania has undertaken to establish the national framework for supporting the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which includes a set of 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), informally reunited under the name of Global Goals. The Global Action Plan, which Romania chooses to support in the coming years, addresses poverty alleviation, combating inequalities, social injustice and protecting the planet by 2030. It is an action plan for people, planet and prosperity, which aims to strengthen a climate of safety and freedom, in which "no one will be left behind" (Strategia..., 2018, p. 13).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is a nonparametric method for estimating the technical efficiency of a set of decision making units (DMUs) in a database using inputs and outputs. The DEA method is used in various fields, such as: industry, agriculture, transport, tourism, banking, education, health, etc. The decision-making units can therefore be: industrial

enterprises, agricultural units, ports, banks, schools or hospitals. Therefore, to measure the efficiency of spatial boundaries, as well as to evaluate the performance of development programs and decision-making units related to sustainable development, there are a lot of studies at international level, including: "Regional sustainable development and spatial effects from the perspective of renewable energy" (Cai et al., 2022), "Urban green development towards sustainability in northwest China: efficiency assessment, spatial-temporal differentiation characters, and influencing factors" (Si et al., 2021), "Spatial structure of China's green development efficiency: a perspective based on social network analysis" (Gao et al., 2022), "Eco-efficiency and effectiveness evaluation toward sustainable urban development in China: a super-efficiency SBM-DEA with undesirable outputs" (Long, 2021), "An analysis on the economic effectiveness of municipalities in Turkey" (Kutlar et al., 2012), "DEA usage in assessing the efficiency of secondary schools in the National Assessment. Case study: Constanța county, Dobrogea, Romania" (Matei, 2023).

Bapat (2006, pp. 8-13) in his book "Spatial efficiency in geography" proposes six types of spatial efficiency: spatial efficiency in location of central places, spatial efficiency in location of routes and movement, spatial efficiency in location of industry, spatial efficiency in shapes and boundaries, spatial efficiency in urban land-use, and spatial efficiency in agricultural land-use. Spatial efficiency in its sense is the ratio between space performance or activity and spatial distance. In this regard, spatial efficiency is proposed with the aim of maximising some spatial activities, such as: land or resource use, moving in space, distributing people, etc., and minimising spatial distance. A more evolved description of the notion of spatial efficiency was made by Tsou and Kuo (2012). They use in their study a large number of factors (inputs and outputs) that influence space activities and not just spatial distance as in the case of the Indian author. Yang et al. (2022) evaluate the effectiveness of urban ecological development in China's Yangtze River delta using data envelope analysis. Also, Huang et al. (2023) use the same method in their analysis of how urban development affects the efficiency of ecological development in China, taking as an example the urban cluster of the Yangtze River economic belt.

Barandak and Demir (2020) analyze in the study "Spatial efficiency towards sustainable development; Case study: provinces of Iran" sustainable development of Iranian provinces from the perspective of spatial efficiency. The average efficiency of these provinces is 0.961, resulting from high efficiency values (1.000) in the border and lateral provinces of the state and lower for those located in the central part, where the minimum efficiency value is recorded, of 0.759 in Isfahan province.

A thorough analysis of socio-economic inequalities in Romania can be found in the report "Unequal Romania. Regional socio-economic disparities in Romania" (Fina et al., 2021) conducted by the Research Institute for Regional and Urban Development in Dortmund. The authors of the report, following a cluster analysis, divide Romania into four distinct regions (clusters), four spatial types called "The Four Romanias". In order of their socio-economic development, these regions are: (1) Bucharest, known as the "economic engine of Romania", (2) dynamic urbanized regions, which include the counties of Timiș, Cluj, Sibiu, Brașov, Iași and Ilfov, both regions having over 25% of the total population of the country, (3) the rural middle of Romania, which comprises 25 counties (e.g. Constanța, Bihor, Gorj, Teleorman, Argeș, Prahova, Covasna, Bistrița-Năsăud etc.) and owns 51% of the population, and (4) old rural and

industrial regions with significant socio-economic challenges, with the 10 counties located mainly near Romania's eastern border, but also in the northwest and southwest border regions (e.g. Tulcea, Brăila, Vaslui, Botoșani, Satu Mare, Caraș-Severin, etc.) and with almost a quarter of the population.

3. SPATIAL EFFICIENCY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

The term *spatial efficiency* has its origin in neoclassical economics, which is based on the theory of value-utility according to which the value of the commodity is not given by the labor embodied in it (the theory of value-labor, admitted by classical economics), but by the utility that the commodity has for the buyer (Coșea, 2005, p. 327). In a general sense, *efficiency* is the completion of a task with minimal time, effort or cost. In other words, it means the geographical arrangement of some components (residences, enterprises, transport, green space, etc.), as well as the relationships between them that minimize the time, effort or costs necessary to carry out economic activities for the entire region (*space*). A spatially efficient arrangement should therefore produce higher economic growth than a less efficient arrangement, providing an advantage over regions with less efficient spatial arrangements (Sarzynski and Levy, 2010, pp. 2-4). Starting from the above definition, spatial efficiency can be expressed through the relationship (Tsou and Kuo, 2012, Kuo and Tsou, 2015):

$$SE = \frac{I_1 \text{ (positive impacts)}}{I_2 \text{ (negative impacts)}} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n O_j}{\sum_{i=1}^m I_i}, \quad j = 1, \dots, n, i = 1, \dots, m \quad (1)$$

where: SE = spatial efficiency; I_1 = positive impacts resulting from the accumulation of current state changes in society and economy, i.e. sum of outputs (O); I_2 = negative impacts resulting from the accumulation of changes in the current status of related natural environmental resources and ecological environment, i.e. sum of inputs (I).

According to the Explanatory Dictionary of the Romanian Language (1996), the term *development* represents "the action of developing and its result". *To develop*, according to the same dictionary, means "to pass through different phases progressively, to a higher stage; to evolve, to transform". The etymology of *sustainable* originates from the French verb *soutenir*, which translates to "to hold up or support" (Brown et al., 1987). The Encyclopaedic Dictionary (2006) defines sustainability as "the quality of an anthropogenic activity to be carried out without exhausting available resources and without destroying the environment, thus without compromising the possibilities of meeting the needs of future generations". When referring to the overall economic development of a country or region, the synonymous term *sustainable development* is usually preferred. The term *sustainable* first appears in Europe in 1713 in the book "Sylvicultura Oeconomica" by the German forester and scientist Hans Carl von Carlowitz. Later, French and English foresters adopted the term associated with tree planting activity in the expression "sustained-yield forestry" (Petre, 2016). The term *sustainability* comes from the field of forestry (Brown et al., 1987), when the German forester Georg Ludwig Hartig, at the end of the eighteenth century, in a definition of forest management, included the idea that "logging in forests must be regulated in such a way that future generations can benefit from it at least as many advantages as the current generation", considering, first of all, that "permanent, constant and equal wood production is carried out annually from the forest" (Murariu and Melu, 2016, p. 41).

Humanity has begun to realize the importance of preserving the environment with the increasing global impact of socio-economic development on it. As a result, several international conferences were organized and reports were drawn up to draw the world's attention to environmental problems, identify global problems and find solutions to them: United Nations Conference in Stockholm in 1972, Brundtland Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) in 1987, which gives a widely accepted definition of sustainable development today, namely "sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (Brundtland, 1987), the Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro in 1992, which elaborated Agenda 21, the World Summit on Sustainable Development (WSSD) or NGO Summit for Earth in Johannesburg in 2002, the Second United Nations Conference in Rio de Janeiro in 2012 (Rio + 20 or Rio Earth Summit 2012), and the September 2015 Summit, which adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which promotes the balance between the three dimensions of sustainable development: economic, social and environmental.

The three pillars on which sustainable development is based are: social sustainability, economic sustainability and environmental sustainability (Radoiu and Batusaru, 2022). The relationship between the three pillars is represented in the figure below.

Figure 1. Relationships between environmental, social and economic sustainability.

(Sursa: Hafizyar și Dheyaaldin, 2019)

The concept of *sustainable spatial development* appeared at the 10th CEMAT Conference (European Conference of Ministers responsible for Spatial/Regional Planning), which took place in Oslo, in 1994, with the theme "Strategy for sustainable regional and spatial development in Europe beyond the year 2000". Sustainable spatial development requires a balance between the resources available to a region and those it uses. The purpose of this development is for sustainable development to be made equitable between the various regions, both vertically (increasing the level of welfare) and horizontally (reducing regional disparities), precisely to avoid as much as possible the development of some to the detriment of others (Petre, 2016). Sustainable spatial development is "that development that ensures a territorial balance of meeting the economic, social and ecological needs of present and future generations at the same

rate" (Petrișor, 2008). Spatial sustainability is closely linked to two other European concepts: territorial cohesion and polycentric development. The "Green Paper on territorial cohesion" (2008) gives new meaning to this concept: "territorial cohesion is about ensuring the harmonious development of all territories and ensuring that their citizens are able to make the most of their inherent characteristics". Polycentric development implies the most uniform distribution of cities in the territory.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. Method

The present study uses a descriptive-analytical method for assessing the spatial efficiency of Romania's counties, as well as that of the development regions in which these counties are included, from the perspective of sustainable development. It uses Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), a nonparametric method for estimating the relative efficiency of a set of DMUs (Decision Making Units) in a database using inputs and outputs, a mathematical method based on linear programming for calculating border efficiency launched by Charnes, Cooper and Rhodes (1978), also known as the CCR model (acronym of the three authors of the model) or the CRS model (Constant Returns to Scale). The study also uses the A-P model by Andersen and Petersen (1993) to assess superefficiency.

The application of the DEA method involves solving the following linear programming task:

$$\begin{aligned} \max w_p &= \sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{rp} \\ \text{subject to: } & \sum_{i=1}^k v_i x_{ip} = 1 \\ & \sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{ri} - \sum_{i=1}^k v_i x_{ij} \leq 0 \quad j = 1, \dots, n \\ & u_r \geq 0 \quad r = 1, \dots, s \\ & v_i \geq 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, k \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where: w_p is the relative efficiency of a decision making unit, x_i and y_r respectively represent input k and output s for n decision making units, v and u represent respectively the weights of the inputs and outputs.

The DEA method calculates for some decision units (efficient units) a maximum score of 1.000 (or 100%), but does not differentiate them by the score obtained by each. Andersen and Petersen (1993) propose a model by which superefficiency is estimated. This model ensures, through the superefficiency score obtained, the comparison of efficient units and their classification according to this score. Therefore, this technique allows an efficient decision unit p to achieve a higher value than the other efficient decision units, by removing the p constraint from the initial model (Barandak and Demir, 2020):

$$\begin{aligned} \max w_p &= \sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{rp} \\ \text{subject to: } & \sum_{i=1}^k v_i x_{ip} = 1 \\ & \sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{ri} - \sum_{i=1}^k v_i x_{ij} \leq 0 \quad j = 1, \dots, n \text{ and } j \neq p \\ & u_r \geq 0 \quad r = 1, \dots, s \\ & v_i \geq 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, k \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

To estimate the spatial efficiency and superefficiency of counties and development regions in Romania by solving the problem of linear programming, the interactive web app deaR-Shiny was used (Benitez et al., 2021).

4.2. Data source

The study calculates the spatial efficiency of Romania's 41 counties, plus Bucharest, as well as the eight development regions. An important feature of the DEA method is the careful choice of variables (inputs - k and outputs - s), since different

sets of variables can lead to different efficiency values. The number of variables used to estimate efficiency also matters, being determined according to the number of decision units (n), because failure to comply with the $n \geq 3$ relationship ($k + s$) will make many decision units reach the limit of efficiency (Barandak and Demir, 2020). Each of the 42 decision making units was evaluated on a set of variables composed of five outputs and five inputs respectively. The category of outputs, which represent the positive impacts in the socio-economic sphere, with benefits on spatial development includes: Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Gross Domestic Product (GDP) - industrial value, hospital beds, forests and vacancies. The five

inputs, which represent negative impacts in the field of natural resources and on the ecological domain (environmental), are: active industrial enterprises, building permits in cities, distributed natural gas, distributed drinking water and public roads.

The data of the study were obtained from the TEMPO-online statistical database of the National Institute of Statistics from different years (2020, 2021 and 2023) (INS, 2023) and from the website of the National Employment Agency for 2023 (ANOFM, 2023). The variables listed above and the source of the data are listed and described in Table 1.

Table 1. Variable model and data source.

No.	Variable	Unit of measurement	Type of variable	Data source / Year
1	Active industrial enterprises	number	input	INS-TEMPO-online / 2021
2	Building permits in urban areas	number	input	INS-TEMPO-online / 2022
3	Distributed natural gas	thousands cubic meters	input	INS-TEMPO-online / 2021
4	Distributed drinking water	thousands cubic meters	input	INS-TEMPO-online / 2021
5	Public roads	kilometers	input	INS-TEMPO-online / 2022
6	GDP (Gross Domestic Product)	million lei	output	INS-TEMPO-online / 2020
7	GDP - industrial value	million lei	output	INS-TEMPO-online / 2020
8	Hospital beds	number	output	INS-TEMPO-online / 2021
9	Forests	hectares	output	INS-TEMPO-online / 2021
10	Job opportunity	number	output	ANOFM / 2023

The county is an administrative-territorial unit of NUTS-III level (Nomenclature of Territorial Statistical Units) in the European Union, made up of cities and rural communes, depending on historical and geographical conditions, with a residence and local bodies that ensure county administration. The eight development regions of Romania (Nord-Vest, Vest, Sud-Vest Oltenia, Centru, Nord-Est, Sud-Est, Sud-Muntenia and București-Ilfov) were created in 1998 and correspond to the NUTS-II level divisions. Each development region consists of a number of counties between four (Vest) and seven (Sud-Muntenia), except for the București-Ilfov region, with two counties. They are not proper administrative-territorial units and do not have legal personality, being only statistical quantities

used to interpret and research regional statistics.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables. It can be easily seen that Bucharest has maximum values for almost all variables (inputs and outputs), except for two of them (public roads and forests, with minimum values), as is natural given the much smaller surface of the capital compared to that of a county, to which is added the small number of vacancies. There are also very large differences between the maximum and minimum values of variables in the case of Bucharest and the other counties (e.g. the two GDPs or distributed natural gas).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of variables.

No.	Variable	Average	Maximum	Minimum	Variation range	Standard deviation	No. of observations
1	Active industrial enterprises	1458	7005 Bucharest	402 Mehedinți	6603	1119	42
2	Building permits in urban areas	379	1606 Ilfov	102 Buzău	1504	272	42
3	Distributed natural gas	228094	2934429 Bucharest	18173 Mehedinți	2916256	442454	42
4	Distributed drinking water	18997	137903 Bucharest	6360 Covasna	131543	20693	42
5	Public roads	2056	3537 Argeș	91 Bucharest	3446	721	42
6	GDP (Gross Domestic Product)	25381	265498 Bucharest	7697 Călărași	257801	39635	42
7	GDP - industrial value	4905	26091 Bucharest	1862 Caraș-Severin	24229	4467	42
8	Hospital beds	3216	22605 Bucharest	831 Tulcea	21774	3430	42
9	Forests	157300	437800 Suceava	600 Bucharest	437200	109218	42
10	Job opportunity	1756	18052 Bihor	212 Covasna	17840	3307	42

In assessing the spatial efficiency of Romania's counties and development regions, according to the DEA-CCR method, each

of these decision units received an efficiency score in the range of zero and one (or between 0% and 100%). Efficient units are

only those units that, depending on the ten variables used, obtain the maximum score one (1.000 or 100%). By distancing units from this score, their spatial efficiency decreases. An inefficient unit is the unit that has failed to improve its development facilities in proportion to the costs incurred per space unit compared to the other units. For efficient decision-making units,

the superefficiency score was also calculated according to the Andersen and Petersen model. Table 3 presents the spatial efficiency and superefficiency scores of Romania's counties, as well as the efficiency and superefficiency of Romania's development regions.

Table 3. Efficiency and superefficiency of counties.

No.	Development region	Efficiency and superefficiency of the development region	County	County efficiency	Superefficiency of the county
1	NORD-VEST	1.829	Bihor	1.000	2.753
2			Bistrița-Năsăud	0.917	0.917
3			Cluj	1.000	1.066
4			Maramureș	0.957	0.957
5			Satu Mare	0.904	0.904
6			Sălaj	0.797	0.797
7	CENTRU	1.134	Alba	0.976	0.976
8			Brașov	0.998	0.998
9			Covasna	1.000	1.364
10			Harghita	1.000	1.069
11			Mureș	0.938	0.938
12			Sibiu	1.000	1.014
13	NORD-EST	1.252	Bacău	0.935	0.935
14			Botoșani	1.000	1.288
15			Iași	1.000	2.338
16			Neamț	0.994	0.994
17			Suceava	1.000	1.064
18			Vaslui	0.978	0.978
19	SUD-EST	0.887	Brăila	0.807	0.807
20			Buzău	1.000	1.356
21			Constanța	0.927	0.927
22			Galați	0.806	0.806
23			Tulcea	1.000	1.258
24			Vrancea	0.845	0.845
25	SUD-MUNTENIA	1.125	Argeș	0.822	0.822
26			Călărași	0.784	0.784
27			Dâmbovița	0.956	0.956
28			Giurgiu	0.858	0.858
29			Ialomița	0.924	0.924
30			Prahova	1.000	1.238
31	Teleorman	1.000	1.053		
32	BUCUREȘTI-ILFOV	30.997	Ilfov	1.000	1.484
33			Bucharest	1.000	106.000
34	SUD-VEST OLTENIA	1.261	Dolj	1.000	1.283
35			Gorj	1.000	1.451
36			Mehedinți	1.000	1.658
37			Olt	0.733	0.733
38			Vâlcea	0.898	0.898
39	VEST	1.374	Arad	0.914	0.914
40			Caraș-Severin	1.000	2.337
41			Hunedoara	1.000	1.158
42			Timiș	1.000	1.238

Figure 2 shows Romania's counties according to their spatial efficiency: efficient counties (score 1.000) and inefficient counties (score below 1.000). Figure 3 and Figure 4 graphically show the efficiency and superefficiency scores of the counties recorded in Table 3. Figure 5 shows the efficiency and superefficiency scores of Romania's eight development regions. Almost half of Romania's counties (20 counties) are spatially efficient (score 1.000). They are located mainly in the western part of the country (e.g. Bihor, Caraș-Severin, Gorj, etc.), while inefficient counties (score below 1.000) are located in the eastern part (e.g. Neamț, Călărași, Constanța, etc.). Brașov

County has the highest value of spatial efficiency among inefficient counties (0.998), and the lowest values (below 0.800) are recorded by Sălaj (0.797), Călărași (0.784) and Olt (0.733) counties. The Andersen and Petersen model ranks the 20 efficient counties (Figure 4). The highest value of these is Bucharest (106.000), where the capital of the country is located. This can be explained by the position that this city holds, as the capital of Romania, which allowed a massive concentration of governmental power, economic activities and knowledge, being the economic engine of the country and by far the winner of the post-socialist transformation process.

Figure 2. Efficient counties and inefficient counties.

Figure 3. Efficiency of counties.

Figure 4. Superefficiency of counties.

Figure 5. Efficiency and superefficiency of development regions.

Taking advantage of this function, together with Ilfov County, with which it forms the București-Ilfov development region, it also registers the highest superefficiency score (30.997), an extraordinarily high score compared to the other development regions that barely pass the score of 1.000 (Figure 5).

The only inefficient region in the country is the Sud-Est region, with a spatial efficiency score of 0.887. Figure 6 shows the current value of GDP, as well as its optimal value for the Sud-Est region, indicating how many million lei this output would have needed for the region to reach the score of 1.000 and to be on the production frontier curve becoming an efficient region. The same alloy of the graph shows the other four outputs of this region (GDP - industrial value, hospital beds, forests, and job opportunity).

Figure 6. Current and optimal GDP values for the Sud-Est region

Figure 5 shows that, except for the București-Ilfov region, the highest superefficiency scores are recorded by the regions located in the west of the country (Nord-Vest, Vest and Sud-Vest Oltenia), compared to the other regions of the country. These results are consistent with the results of studies on socio-economic disparities between Romania's development regions. Thus, in the report prepared by the World Bank entitled "Economic dynamics of cities in Romania (2020, p. 13) "municipalities and cities in western and central Romania generally have larger functional urban areas than their counterparts in the east or south - probably benefiting from the proximity to the western border". Cities with large functional areas (e.g. Cluj-Napoca, Timișoara, Oradea, Arad, Brașov, Sibiu, Iași, etc.) are also cities with strong economies, engines of regional development. The authors of the study "Unequal Romania. Regional socio-economic disparities in Romania" (2021, p. 11) makes a spatial typology of socio-economic disparities in Romania, identifying four regions. The fourth region, called "old rural and industrial regions with significant socio-economic challenges", comprises most of the counties located near the country's eastern border.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Sustainable development is today one of the desiderata of the contemporary world, a challenge at regional and global level. Geographical space must quickly find a way of reconciling its components, thus avoiding damage to the environment, but at the same time ensuring the socio-economic development of that geographical space. The present study proposes an assessment of the spatial efficiency of Romania's counties and development regions from the perspective of sustainable development. The basis for spatial efficiency evaluation was Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), a nonparametric method for estimating the relative efficiency of a set of DMUs (Decision Making Units) using a set of inputs and outputs, a mathematical method based on linear programming. For the division of efficient DMUs (those with a score of 1.000), the A-P model made by Andersen and Petersen was used, the one that evaluates superefficiency

(units with scores above 1.000). The results of the study are graphically transposed into four maps showing the efficiency and superefficiency of counties and development regions. The average efficiency of Romania's counties is 0.945. Efficient counties are located mainly in the western part of the country and less in its eastern part. The highest score was obtained by Bucharest (106.000) and the lowest by Olt County (0.733). The average efficiency of development regions is 0.986. As in the case of counties, development regions, depending on the score obtained, show the same arrangement on the west-east axis: higher superefficiency scores are registered by the development regions in the western part of the country compared to those located in the east. The highest score of superefficiency was obtained by the București-Ilfov region (30.997). The only inefficient region with the lowest spatial efficiency score (0.887) is the Sud-Est region.

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